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Women's Micro-Entrepreneurial Home-Working as a Post-Fordist 'Magical Solution' to the Work-Life Relationship

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One response by middle class women across the global West to the competing demands of post-Fordist conditions of both paid and unpaid work is the outsourcing of domestic labour to less economically empowered and often precariously employed women. Another response, not mutually exclusive to this and which is also on the rise, is the more 'do it yourself' one of career-shifting to work from home. Enabled by the worldwide distribution affordances of the internet, increasing numbers of creative producers of the handmade, the majority of them middle class women, are working from home as sole traders, often as a means by which to balance caring responsibilities with paid employment and/or bring in top-up family income. The very taken-for-grantedness of communications and other digital technologies as everyday devices sees them playing a determining role in normalising the home office and home studio, additionally collapsing the already porous relationship between work and other aspects of life. Further, and at a more specifically gendered level, being able to work from home and/or flexibly has been embraced by many women as an important compromise between paid work and unpaid domestic responsibilities. This is especially so for a particular cohort of largely educated, Western middle class women in

their late 20s and into their 30s—key child-bearing years—among whom “[m]otherhood itself is [currently] being venerated in a way not seen since the hypernatalist 1950s” (Matchar, 2013: 3-4).

While feminists have long challenged the invisibility of women’s home-based—both paid and unpaid—labour which has underpinned industrial capitalism’s social contract, middle class women are now being directly interpellated as entrepreneurial subjects, and women’s home-based craft micro-enterprise is on the rise globally. Websites such as market leader Etsy but also hundreds of less high profile sitesⁱ, reflect and have enabled an explosion during the Global Financial Crisis (GFC) of micro-entrepreneurial home-based design craft labour. In this way, the post-Etsyⁱⁱ economy can be feared to be a ‘wolf in sheep’s clothing’, facilitating the shift of relatively privileged women out of the public workplace and back into traditional roles within the home as though the publication of *The Feminine Mystique* had never happened. But I argue that the contemporary online craft economy is more logically locatable within the broader contemporary moment’s extension of the “ordinary and normalised presence of financial capitalism”, including its “entrepreneurial subjectivities”, into the everyday of the domestic and home-life (Allon, 2014: 13). As Allon argues, these “changes have reconfigured the home as a scene for capital accumulation that requires new kinds of economic management and financial calculation, in other words, new kinds of domestic labour” (Allon, 2014: 14). And while Allon was not referring in any detail specifically to women’s home-based micro-enterprise, this chapter will argue that alongside other strategies of negotiating credit and debt, the contemporary online craft marketplace is clearly a manifestation of these larger patterns within the global post-Fordist economy.

Following Adkins, these post-Fordist business practices are best seen as a “folding of the economy into society” (Adkins, 2012: 621), rather than as a simple return of women to the kitchen marking the re-emergence of the previous Fordist sexual contract which required women’s “unpaid domestic, caring and servicing labour in the private sphere” in order to enable the maintenance and reproduction of men’s labour power in the realm of paid work (Adkins and Dever, 2014: 56). Rather, it represents a new and relatively privileged negotiation of the post-Fordist social contract whereby new configurations of gender are being brought into being which necessitate a “retraditionalisation of gender” in forms sympathetic to contemporary capitalist and familial relations and identities (Adkins, 1999: 136). In the service of their own aims to maximise national fiscal productivity, Western governments are increasingly acknowledging the loss of human capital that can arise when skilled women leave the paid workforce on account of parenting responsibilities rendered impossible to negotiate by the ‘chrono-normativity’ⁱⁱⁱ of traditional paid work temporality (Grabham, 2014: 73; see also Ekinsmyth, 2011; 2012; 2013a; 2013b). A key strategy being employed in Anglo-American nations to enable this is less-so the extension of quality, accessible childcare as is available to women in a number of Nordic countries, but rather the encouragement of a more entrepreneurial and privatised response in the form of home-based business enterprises (Ekinsmyth, 2011 & 2013a). Craft distribution and marketing sites such as Etsy can therefore slot easily into this environment, and in a very post-Fordist way via the handmade continue the long, but previously less visible, tradition of middle-class women using their creative skills to contribute from home to the family income (Turney, 2009).

Design Craft Self-Employment and Home-based Labour as the Answer to Work-Life

Balance

Beyond the straight-through education path taken especially by many professional studio, art or design craft professionals, there are two other key stage of life moments which precipitate women's 'downshifting' into small-scale creative enterprise: having children and (semi)retirement (Luckman, 2012 and 2015). Given the youthful 'hipster' appeal of the online design craft marketplace, parenthood-related origin stories are plentiful throughout the personal stories of the makers in the contemporary craft economy. The public performance of the craft producer's personal identity as part and parcel of the consumer value of their products, and as proof of the stripped-back value chain of buying 'direct' from the maker, has become an essential part of the home-based maker's online marketing identity. As the highest profile website in the design craft marketplace, Etsy has led the way in terms of driving up the aesthetic and marketing skills expectations consumers now have of makers. While each Etsy 'store' includes information on and a profile of the maker, raising this maker profile to an even greater level of depth and sophistication has been Etsy's 'Featured Seller', now 'Featured Shop', blog which gives individual sellers a high-profile location on the parent website.^{iv} Updated approximately three times a week with new profiles, this archive furnishes us with a rich public representation of the additional affective and aesthetic labour required by post-Fordist craft producers.^v The labour performed in these seller blogs on Etsy especially but also elsewhere where female sellers are predominant, is labour is required precisely to collapse the work-life spatial and ontological divide through the hidden labour of presenting perfect families and beautiful spaces while

keeping a workplace as well as a home. The image presented in these profiles very much parallels that emerging in other research into emerging models of female entrepreneurship made possible through the affordances of digital technology in the home (Ekinsmyth, 2011; 2012; 2013a; 2013b).

There is a consistent pattern to the narratives offered in the profiles, and a notable aspect of this is the emphasis on a moment of revelation or at least of the need for change in one's work–life relationship. Children are notably present in the text around the telling of the story of the value of being able to work from home while children are young – a crafty way to 'have it all'. So forget the oft-cited classic image of the modern career woman as a striding be-suited professional, laptop in one hand, baby in the other. In this contemporary and very public shopfront operating at the frontline of new production and consumption models enabled by digital technology, the contemporary figure of the successful middle-class, generally heterosexual and white, working woman is someone simultaneously of the home and of the global alternative economic marketplace, giving rise to unrealistic images of a seemingly blissful hipster domestic perfection. Notably for our purposes here, as of July 2012 these profiles tended to be presented as a first person narrative starting with a personal introduction along the lines of: "My name is ... and I am ..." Or more informally: "Hi, I'm ..., and my shop is ...".^{vi} In the post-Etsy craft economy individualisation itself is thus institutionalised in the form of a new 'standard' career biography where having children is no longer a career *interruption*; rather it is now a pivotal moment of life re-evaluation to be embraced. Work–life relationships, which were once seen as complex and problematic, are presented as now reconciled in the world of women's micro-enterprise. As befits a (self-)

promotional strategy, in the Etsy Featured Shop profile the narrative performance becomes tightly bounded, following a logical narrative for others to adopt. This is a combined life–career narrative presented putatively as a journey, but when the repetition of key motifs and the lack of individuality in the experiences becomes apparent, we can see how the conditions of post-Fordism and its institutions – old and new – themselves bring into being new models of career narrative to be adopted, embraced and internalised. These new narratives allow the individual’s multiple and *previously* competing pulls between work and family to be (apparently) marvellously reconciled.

As a number of commentators are increasingly arguing (Hassoun, 2012; Yeatman, 2014; Walkerdine, 2003), contemporary feminist and post-Fordist—‘or ‘hyper-capitalist’ (Yeatman, 2014)—entrepreneurial subjectivities are actually far less hostile to one another than we may like to imagine. Indeed Gill identifies postfeminism as “a distinctive sensibility linked to neoliberalism” (Gill, 2011). And Yeatman observes how discourses of ‘control’ and ‘choice’, often enabled by new technologies, strongly speak to women’s desires including the reconciliation of paid work and family responsibilities: “Contemporary feminism cannot escape an unhappy state of co-option in relation to the combined forces of a hyper-capitalism and modern technology. Where the former subjects everyone and everything to an instrumental logic of commodification, the latter exemplifies a distinctly modern fantasy of control.” (Yeatman, 2014: 85) All this serves to give rise to a scenario where some *prima facie* fortunate women come to be McRobbie’s “privileged subjects of social change” (McRobbie, 2009: 15).

Nowhere are all the above movements clearer than in the recent rise of the figure of the so-called 'mumpreneur' (Bryant, 2013; Duberley and Carrigan, 2012; Ekinsmyth, 2011; 2012; 2013a; 2013b; Nel, Maritz and Thongprovati, 2010). Ekinsmyth defines 'mumpreneurialism' thus: "Embracing, rather than contesting, the role of 'mother' it is a business practice that attempts to recast the boundaries between productive and reproductive work." (Ekinsmyth, 2011: 104) More than simply a category which encompasses any woman who happens to simultaneously be a mother and small business entrepreneur, mumpreneurs explicitly seek to creatively merge the "specialities of mothering with those of business practice" in order to accommodate and prioritise the former (Ekinsmyth, 2011: 105). In short, they are a "group of entrepreneurs whose self-defined rationales and drivers originate predominantly or significantly from the realm of 'reproduction' rather than 'production'" (Ekinsmyth, 2011: 104). While significant debate as to the usefulness, indeed the potential downsides of the use of the phrase remain (Ekinsmyth, 2013a), it is valuable to the extent that it opens up discussion into the ways in which existing definitions of entrepreneurship are premised on a particular heroic masculine norm and its use thus enables the consideration of alternative models, including ones as concerned with *reproduction* as production (Ekinsmyth, 2011). Demographically Ekinsmyth's mumpreneurs parallel the women who dominate the online craft marketplace on sites such as Etsy in that they tend to be middle class, middle aged, living with a partner, have left professional employment and white (Ekinsmyth, 2011: 107). As in earlier research into women's home-working, she notes that the women in her study despite the potent 'have it all' myths of home-working, also found it difficult to simultaneously undertake paid work and looking after children, thus they tended to organise their business time around time children spend in childcare or school (or asleep) (Ekinsmyth, 2013a: 2).

In the contemporary craft economy there can be, discursively at least, a strong sense of elements of a new traditionalism or, more specifically, “New Domesticity” (Matchar, 2013), which writer and journalist Emily Matchar defines it in her book as “the re-embrace of home and hearth by those who have the means to reject these things. It’s the MBA who quits her corporate gig to downsize to a solar-powered renovated barn. It’s the twentysomething New Yorker who spends her evenings blogging about her latest baking project rather than hitting the clubs”, significantly here, it is also iconically she argues: “the young mom who, after her too-short maternity leave, decides to try to make extra money selling her knitting on Etsy rather than go back to work” (Matchar, 2013: 12). All this new-found interest in domestic production is fuelled by a perfect storm of environmentalism; declining full-time or decent part-time job opportunities, including for the once more secure educated middle classes; the politically charged championing of ‘women’s arts’, especially the much-maligned fibre arts of knitting and crochet; as well as a genuine desire to be ‘good mothers’.

Regardless of how any individual woman and her community may define ‘good mothering’, around the global West it tends involves a greater level of ‘presentism’ than is normally possible with a full-time paid job undertaken at a site outside the home. Especially in light of middle class normative expectations of an “increasingly intensive standard of parenting”, this emphasis is seen by some as a swing back by Gen X parents against the perceived dominant mode of ‘latch-key’ absent parenting of their own youth (Matchar, 2013: 15).

Certainly, regardless of the origins, as Barbara Pocock has written, societal pressures around mothering remain powerful:

While women question the ideal of a 'proper mother', they agree that a mythology of 'proper mothering' runs deep in society – including in their own homes. Clearly, women mother in diverse ways and not all carry the same version of 'proper mothering' in their minds. However, there are entrenched and powerful expectations about 'proper mothers' that shape children's expectations as well as those of the extended community and family, and encourage guilt when they cannot be achieved. (Pocock, 2003: 75; see also Ekinsmyth, 2013a & 2013b where she speaks of the pressure to engage in 'intensive mothering')

Further, "a 'proper mother' is one with a lot of time and flexibility to be available to her children, whose job is not pitted against children's needs, or non-negotiable workplace demands. This caricature is alive in women's minds and society despite the fact that many cannot 'live up' to it" (Pocock, 2003: 77). Such "'good mothering' hegemonies" Ekinsmyth argues need to be more strongly contested and politicized in contemporary Western cultures (Ekinsmyth, 2013a: 3). Adding an additional encumbrance to this already burdensome picture, this level of being an available parent is now coupled with the post-Fordist expectation that all adults be engaged in paid work or, at least, be ready to do so, if unemployed for example (see Adkins, 2012), with the effect that "labour market participation for women has become a moral duty" (Adkins and Jokinen, 2008: 146). Given this, home-based micro-entrepreneurship can be a license to negotiate staying at home in a socio-economic context where, as Hochschild earlier noted, "the role of housewife has lost its allure, [with the effect that] the wives who "just" stay at home have developed the defensiveness of the downwardly mobile." (Hochschild, 1997: 244)

But for many women the simple reality is, as McRobbie writes, that with “the onset of maternity the social compromise applies both in the home and in the workplace. Jobs which are compatible with the demands of the home are preferred over those which might have more advantageous career ladders” (McRobbie, 2007: 730). Certainly Ekinsmyth’s empirical research reflects the negotiation of this reality of needing to ‘downshift’ away from ‘high flying’ professional employment in order to accommodate the realities of parental responsibilities and the persistent social expectation that mothers should be primary carers:

Such re-evaluation was often essential for these women. For many, previous jobs and careers offered no workable/acceptable mode through which to comfortably combine work and parenthood. After the birth of their first or subsequent children, many found their previous working lifestyles unsustainable/risk-laden. Others were sidelined into jobs and roles that were less fulfilling than those held before childbirth. The predominant story these women told was one that revealed the murky territory between compulsion to change and choice. As one interviewee succinctly put it, “I was just trying to find something that worked around life (Ekinsmyth, 2011: 109; see also Ekinsmyth, 2013b).

But even in this new realm of self-employed enterprise, professional stigmas against home-working and its associated simultaneous negotiation of paid work and parenthood remain with her respondents observing that they are not taken seriously as when children can be heard in the background when on the phone, with the result being that they go to lengths to avoid this scenario in terms of how they spatially operate within and beyond the home (for

example, making phone calls while waiting in the car for the school pick-up) (Ekinsymth, 2013a & 2013b).

Women's Micro-Entrepreneurial Home-Working as a Post-Fordist 'Magical Solution'

Given the complex mix of socio-economic expectations operating upon contemporary women it is no wonder that those women with the means to do so are seeing working from home as, to borrow a concept from subcultural studies, a kind of post-Fordist 'magical solution' (Cohen, 1981) given the unfinished business of unequal domestic labour responsibilities in the heterosexual household. Within the body of early work on subcultures, subcultural participation was identified as an explicitly working class phenomenon which offered the young dispossessed a 'magical solution' to the contradictions of their lived, class-bound, experience at a time of great change within inner-urban British working class communities. The phrase first arose in Phil Cohen's "Subcultural Conflict and Working-Class Community" (1981), which was based on a study of traditional working class communities in London's east end which were being demolished, and community members displaced into smaller houses, often in high rise blocks, which sought to replicate the middle class ideal of domesticity based on nuclear—not extended—families. This also had the effect of dismantling key community infrastructure as informally manifest in the old public spaces of the street, shop and pub. In such an environment of change and heightened disempowerment, young people were seen to turn to the symbolic structures of subcultures as a performative means by which to seek to reconcile the situation they found themselves in. In the words of Phil Cohen:

The succession of subcultures which this parent [working class inner-London] culture generated can thus all be considered so many variations on a central theme - the contradiction, at an ideological level, between traditional working-class puritanism and the new hedonism of consumption; at an economic level, between a future as part of the socially mobile elite or as part of the new lumpen proletariat. (Cohen, 1981: 82-83)

Of course symbolic reconciliation does not change the fundamental situation. It is a de Certeauian 'making do'; a *tactic* of negotiation of their life by the relatively powerless, rather than a *strategy* of the powerful (de Certeau, 1988). But this is not to necessarily take away its value or power. Within subcultural studies while the idea of the magical solution has been critiqued for its obvious weakness—it means subcultures do not actually bring about structural change, indeed they may well dissipate the will to do so—it has remained an important concept to the degree that such symbolic action can and did enable people to personally survive and negotiate their circumstances. It may not be a maintainable long-term strategy just as home-working is not for many women who may see it as a compromise, a stop-gap measure in between the birth of children and them becoming more independent or starting school. This sense of working from home as rational if not ideal 'magical solution' is reinforced in existent research into women's' experiences of home-based employment. While observing that men tended to list positive motivations such as 'freedom' as drivers of their own desire to work from home, Phizacklea and Wolkowitz 'were struck by the fact' that the advantages of working from home most often cited by women "[a]ddressed the work constraints themselves and were not advantages in and of themselves. Rather than focussing on their constrained options, respondents focused on

how home-based work helped them to deal with them.” (Phizacklea and Wolkowitz, 1995: 79)

It is in this complex, fraught and contradictory way that the magical solution of home-based employment can be seen as an instance of what Lauren Berlant identifies as ‘cruel optimism’ (Berlant, 2011). Clearly resonating with the marketing-focussed and thus public-facing success stories of the Etsy Featured Seller blogs, as well as wider celebratory stories of work-life reconciliation achieved via home-based craft micro-enterprise, her project exploring cruel optimism has as its centre

[t]hat moral-intimate-economic thing called “the good life.” Why do people stay attached to conventional good-life fantasies—say, of enduring reciprocity in couples, families, political systems, institutions, markets, and at work—when the evidence of their instability, fragility, and dear cost abounds? Fantasy is the means by which people hoard idealizing theories and tableaux about how they and the world “add up to something.” (Berlant, 2011: 2)

Therefore, “[w]hatever the *experience* of optimism in particular, then, the affective structure of an optimistic attachment involves a sustaining inclination to return to the scene of fantasy that enables you to expect that *this* time, nearness to *this* thing will help you or a world to become different in just the right way.” (Berlant, 2011: 2) So no matter how complex and ultimately still difficult the reality of home-based micro-entrepreneurship may be, it should therefore come as no surprise at all that women who are in a position to do so continue to embrace the ‘magical solution’ ‘making do’ position of home-based micro-

enterprise to 'resolve' competing work-life responsibilities afforded women under conditions of post-Fordism. Especially given women continue to bear the burden of responsibility for 'performing' this reconciliation in the absence of wider socio-cultural change (Fudge and Owens, 2006).

Homeworking operates within a post-Fordist new social contract which requires the participation of women in the paid workforce, but which offsets the burden of responsibility for increased work hours and presumptions of ongoing contact and 'flexibility' onto the individual worker. Under wider conditions of post-Fordist precarity it represents in many ways a contemporary (re)negotiation of, or concession to, the neo-liberalised 'good life'. In this way "the ordinary [is] a zone of convergence of many histories, where people manage the incoherence of lives that proceed in the face of threats to the good life they imagine" (Berlant 2011: 10). Thus it clearly manifests strong elements of Beck and Beck-Gernsheim's 'institutionalized individualism'. This is a social condition not freely chosen whereby people are required "to create, to stage manage, not only one's own biography but the bonds and networks surrounding it and to do this amid changing preferences and at successive stages of life, while constantly adapting to the conditions of the labour market, the education system, the welfare state and so on". (Beck and Beck-Gernsheim, 2002: 4) The individual is "increasingly expected to produce context for themselves. The designing of life, of a self-project, is deeply rooted as both a social norm and cultural obligation" (Elliott and Lemert, 2009: 13)

Thus it is impossible not to see the rise of women's home-based micro-enterprise as a direct shift away from reasonable social expectations of employment and/or a social safety net to protect people between jobs. Here the burden is placed onto the individual to create their own employment options as part of the wider project of fashioning the conditions of their own life. So given that the contemporary craft economy is growing alongside increasing unemployment, it is reasonable to fear that this largely white, middle-class cultural economy is simply another manifestation of post-Fordist precarity and institutionalised individualisation. Certainly the popular media is already starting to point out explicit links between dwindling employment and rising self-employment figures (Fisher, 2014). Home-based self-employment can thus be justifiably identified as a twenty-first-century example of how "the "family" more and more becomes the rubbish bin for all the social problems around the world that cannot be solved in any other way" (Beck and Beck-Gernsheim, 2002: xxiii), thus re-embedding women in new socialities (Adkins, 1999: 136). The risks of the contemporary world are thus built into socio-economic systems to be increasingly borne by the individual and not society; by the individual not the collective.

In keeping with Beck and Beck-Gernsheim's (2002) mapping of second modernity's individualisation, personal and business failure also remain largely invisible within the discursive world of the contemporary craft economy. This is despite the reality of high numbers of small business failures, not to mention the vagaries of personal lives; difficulties notoriously exacerbated by financial pressure. As the state recedes and the entrepreneurial individual has to step in themselves "institutional authorities and mechanisms are absolved of responsibility for entrepreneurial failure. Faced with a multiplicity of discourses that reinforce the autonomy, and thus potential culpability, of the 'enterprising self', success

and failure are understood as a triumphs and tragedies of individual design” (Banks, 2007: 63). Once again, the financial and personal burden of capital start-up is borne here by the individual, and, in a world where failure is inherent yet hidden, it is the individual once again who bears responsibility for ‘pulling themselves up by their bootstraps’. Thus home-based craft micro-entrepreneurship occupies a particular niche within larger patterns of individualisation. Indeed, in some ways Beck and Beck-Gernsheim foretold the rise of marketplaces such as those flowing around the handmade: “[i]s the age of mass products and mass consumption coming to an end with the pluralization of lifestyles and must the economy and industry adapt themselves to products and product fashions that can be combined individually, with corresponding methods of production?” (Beck and Beck-Gernsheim, 2002: 16). While the Etsy Featured Shop profiles are full of positive stories of choice, satisfaction, achievement and control, for many self-employment is a licence for low or no income. Women remain particularly vulnerable with self-employment profits replicating wage and salary patterns whereby women earn on average less than their male counterparts. Across all sectors of the UK economy in 2012, for example, self-employed women earned 40 per cent less than self-employed men (Fisher, 2014). Further as successive research into the actual experience of working from home have demonstrated, self-employment is not a simple story of idyllic work–life negotiations and flexibility; financially it can also mean endless deferral of economic rewards and accrual of debt, but at least for a while sustained by the fact of engaging in self-fulfilling work. With this comes not only a resultant lack of job and income security, but the loss of holiday and sick leave, union support, workplace protection, employer superannuation and, especially important for those in nations without strong state-supported healthcare programs, of employer-sponsored health insurance. Thus, as Banks has written:

in this schema, not only does the individual become the focus and target of disciplinary discourses and practices that require reflexive self-monitoring but also as an active subject must learn to 'make their own life' in the institutional contexts laid down by governmental authorities. Actors are encouraged to believe that they (and not social structures) are the authors of fate; capable beings that script their own actions, and indeed, must actively do so in order to achieve the promise of a meaningful and rewarding life. (Banks, 2007: 46)

It is thus not surprising that a simultaneous discourse of both 'risk' and 'empowerment' permeates many of the 2013 Etsy Featured Shop profiles. Within this, the 'networked publics' (boyd, 2011) of online craft marketplaces such as Etsy are seen as modern but inclusive takes on the guild structures and local communities of old, enabling producers to 're-embed' themselves into collective structures precisely at the point of experiencing Beck and Beck-Gernsheim's 'institutionalized individualism'. As engaged with by users, they are a site for 'altruistic individualism' (Beck and Beck-Gernsheim, 2002), offering solidarity, support and community. Within the modern world of 'risk' and micro-enterprise they are seen as empowering, affording the increased confidence and capacity to challenge oneself by starting one's own business.

Therefore a very real and significant concern which needs to be at the forefront of any analysis of the economic possibilities and limits of the contemporary craft economy is that full-time sustainable craft micro-enterprise is being sold to women in particular as the answer to secure employment. That is, the problem lies not in small, local economies and

micro-enterprises implicitly (even in spite of their capacity for self-exploitation), but rather the way in which, in an uncertain and fluid globalised economic world, self-employment is being deployed and becoming institutionalised as an individualised carrot to wave in front of the noses of exhausted, over-committed parents. Self-employment in this way can operate as a twenty-first-century poorhouse; that is, a holding pattern to take pressure off contemporary employment patterns, including many people working hours far in excess of those they desire for family-friendliness, and others simply not working enough to sustain themselves and their families. The situation is particularly acute for those less economically, culturally and socially able to insulate themselves from failure. Some will succeed, but many will not. All will be expected to make sacrifices^{vii}. The competing tensions, the push and pull, of making as desirable paid creative work are palpable and fraught with individualised risk as new generations of largely female, educated, middle-class makers even in the global West live in hope of one day being able to have enough capital to downshift into a family-friendly making micro-enterprise.

This is where the 'out' of the magical solution can be both politically dangerous but also possibly valuable. The growing experience of homeworking has the potential to not simply uncritically celebrate domestic labour, but also to raise it back to visibility, especially parental labor. But this needs to be undertaken critically rather than via unexamined celebration of women's homeworking. For the larger context is, as Matchar has written from the specific perspective of the United States but it is a situation which parallels that encountered across many nations of the global West:

[t]he media did not invent female workplace dissatisfaction. But it has enshrined the idea that work-life balance is impossible and that mothers generally find it more satisfying to stay home. For decades, mainstream American newspapers and magazines have harped on the impossibility of “having it all” and delivered dewy-eyed “opt-out” stories about stay-at-home moms “so in love” with their babies that they can’t possibly imagine going back to work. (Matchar, 2013: 178)

Importantly, as she continues on,

[t]he problem is that the media rarely discusses the real reasons behind why women leave their jobs. We hear a lot about the desire to be closer to the children, the love of crafting and gardening, and making food from scratch. But reasons like lack of maternity leave, lack of affordable day care, lack of job training, and unhappiness with the 24/7 work culture—well, those aren’t getting very much airtime. (Matchar, 2013: 179)

Decades of empirical research into paid work in the middle class home has shown that the myth of working from home that is sold or presumed by middle class workers (as distinct, for example, to piece workers) has a strong sense of 'being there for family' as simply requiring physical presence, not any focus nor specific investment of time or knowledge. It is presented as something that can be done while also fully engaged in paid work. This clearly turns out not to be the case, rather flexibility within extremely long working days seen as the 'win' here, as women work from home around childcare provided by others (in various forms including formal schooling). Etsy and websites like it as a key part of their business models are selling the dream of a perfect life—to both sellers and buyers—as much, if not moreso, than craft items themselves. In so doing the stories on websites like Etsy reinforce a

particular idealized and unproblematic 'you can have it all' image of home-working as unequivocally positive and seemingly easy to negotiate. So given the transformations in what post-Fordist domestic labour is and does, what we now also need are new narratives based on women's actual, un-airbrushed, experiences which in the acknowledgement that one cannot be simultaneously a fully engaged parent *and* paid worker can potentially open up ways through which to articulate the need for greater value to be afforded to childcare in the contemporary reproduction of not only the household, but also the wider economy.

Key here is the fact that the 'making do' magical solution means that while "[b]usiness can now be done differently, [this] enables gender "not to be done differently"," (Ekinsmyth, 2013a: 541). Similarly, the family-unfriendly workplaces in which a significant proportion of paid staff work outside the home can also remain unchanged. It is also important to acknowledge a point of departure from Berlant's framework here; while cruel optimism is cruel precisely because it "exists when something you desire is actually an obstacle to your flourishing" (Berlant, 2011: 1; see also 24), home-based micro-enterprise is, for some women, a genuinely if not always happy then at least successful reconciliation of competing aspects of their lives. These are the subjects of precarity whom, like Berlant's protagonists, "have chosen primarily not to fight, but to get caught up in a circuit of adjustment and gestural transformation in order to stay in proximity to some aspirations that had gotten attached to the normative good life" (Berlant, 2011: 249). But rather than undermine the cruelty of the magical solution, instead this negotiation reinforces the cruelty of the dream to those who cannot realistically or successfully buy into it. In a world where the winding back of 'jobs for life' requires that "[w]ell developed career stories are becoming

increasingly important for individuals as they navigate an unstable and unpredictable labour market” (Meijers and Lengelle, 2012: 157), those with the capacity to “re-‘story’ his/her identifications around work will be more able to navigate the changing world of work, make meaning and sense of career changes” (Meijers and Lengelle, 2012: 158). Relatively globally empowered women thus have something of a ‘way out’ of the conflicts of paid and parental work, albeit a highly compromised ‘out’, and the need for greater recognition of unequal access to such opportunities reinforces Eisenstein’s call for greater feminist cross-class alliances (Eisenstein, 2009: 213). Thus the real danger here is less the return of women to the home as it the easing of political pressure from globally relatively empowered women for deeper change which would gesture towards a situation whereby all men and women can ‘do gender’ (and work) ‘differently’.

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ⁱ It is not possible to provide an exhaustive list of all these sites, but, for example, they include (the nation listed in brackets indicates the country where the website is based or started, but not the limit of its market): ArtFire, ‘Global commerce with a local perspective. We are ArtFire’ (USA) <http://www.artfire.com/>; Big Cartel, ‘Big Cartel provides you with your own independent store to sell your stuff online’ (USA) <http://bigcartel.com/>; Blue Caravan, ‘[ethical] Design Market’ (Australia) <http://www.bluecaravan.net/pages/about/>; Bouf, ‘design-led living’ (UK) <https://www.bouf.com/>; ClickforArt, ‘Limited Edition Art, Art Prints, Canvas Prints & Limited Edition Homewares’ (UK) <http://www.clickforart.com/>; DaWanda, ‘products with love’, ‘the unique marketplace’ (Germany) <http://en.dawanda.com/>; Folksy, ‘Modern British Craft’ (UK) <http://folksy.com/>; Hand-Made.com.au, ‘Your place to buy and sell all things hand-made, vintage upcycled and supplies’ (Australia) <https://www.hand-made.com.au/>; iCraft, ‘Creativity without borders’ (Canada) <http://icraftgifts.com/>; Lilyshop (USA) <http://www.lilyshop.com/>; Madeit, ‘the handmade market open all day every day’ (Australia) <http://www.madeit.com.au/>; Not on the High Street, ‘for a life less ordinary’ (UK) <http://www.notonthehighstreet.com/>; Red Bubble, ‘Buy Shiny Independent Designs on Super-Great Products’ (USA and Australia) <http://www.redbubble.com/>; Supermarket, ‘Great design. Straight from designers’ (USA) <http://supermarkethq.com/browse/everything>; Zibbet, ‘Your place to buy unique, handmade products, direct from the maker’ (USA) <http://www.zibbet.com/>

ⁱⁱ I employ the phrase ‘post-Etsy’ to indicate, temporally, how the contemporary craft economy is being impacted by the run-away success of online selling generally, and Etsy in particular. Etsy’s game-changing role is significant not only economically, but also aesthetically and socio-culturally in terms of how it is pushing consumer and marketplace expectations around marketing, business skills development and setting the tone for the

presentation of the making self. Given Etsy is, at the time of writing, still very much going strong it is in no way a reference to an ‘after Etsy’ moment following its demise.

iii “a working day facilitated by women’s social reproduction” (Grabham 2014, p. 73), that is women’s unpaid reproductive work in the domestic sphere.

iv <https://blog.etsy.com/en/tags/featured-shop/>

v As of July 2014 there were 1,150 profiles in the archive, clearly evidencing the emergence of greater levels of professionalism (in text but most markedly in the accompanying photographs), and even of a particular kind of ‘Etsy aesthetic’ since the first entry in October 2005.

vi See Adkins (2002, 2013) for critiques of both the prevalence of, and ideological presumptions dominant in, individual work–life narratives and discourses in the contemporary post-Fordist knowledge economy.

vii For just one real-world experience of this see the article; ‘The Young, Skint and Self-employed Need a Radical New Labour Market’, *The Guardian*, 21 July, by Paul Mason.